
Historical process and new horizon in contemporary geopolitics

Dr.Mohammadreza Shahidipak¹

¹Professor assistant Islamic Azad University Central Tehran Branch ,Departement Humanity

Abstract: Geopolitics is a direct function of historical process of man in space; Geopolitical actors of state are placed in land that nature has imposed on man. Taking this space that shapes states over time by changing of weather. A space whose dimensions are weather, elevations, being enclosed or coastal. These spaces are not permanent and may be destroyed by loss and destruction of one of dimensions of space. In this research, hypothesis is that in science of geopolitics, relationship between politics and space is constantly changing, and its actors change and are therefore unstable. Any kind of geopolitical thinking should be based on reality of history to ensure its stability. Geographical societies of world are like RGS-IBG, should define new geopolitical horizons useful for humanity and world community, when more than two centuries have passed since geopolitical golden age, it seems that history has turned to that era again, because in fact, history of states are like small Russian dolls placed inside each other, and giants of global economy of China and Russia are in middle east region, which is a ready-to-explode as gunpowder barrel, has been activated, as if powers are seeking new horizons in geopolitics to ensure world peace, to create new dimensions in geopolitics by imposing peace from below. Because vast space extends from Europe to China and from Atlantic Ocean to Himalayas, there is a place of constant danger, and if a special power like Russia, China, Othman, &... flourishes in age of Tsar &... While new form of civilization is emerging, historian of civilization, Toynbee(1975) proposed transnational law to protect it.

Key Words: Toynbee; Geography, RGS-IBG, Geopolitics

Introduction

History is the oldest human science and the source of human knowledge. Since time immemorial, history, like nature and man, has been one of the sources of knowledge and the acquisition of human awareness, and the course of human life in the present and the future has been determined by history. Herodotus, the historian, directed Roman policies. . At the macro level, history also has a geopolitical strategy. This article aims to show this phenomenon of human superiority in contemporary events that are happening by explaining the historical roots.

1-Changing and history

There is no geopolitics without history, history is the main material and foundation of geopolitics. And history is the puzzle of changes and the treasury of changes. History works under the influence of factors and causality is current in history, this causality is the guarantee of permanent changes) 2020) The main problem of this research is that history still governs changes and the root of changes can be traced in historical research. And institutions like RGS can analyze and analyze the history of the change guide at any point and change its evaluation according to the interests. The main reason for the interest in historiography in the current movement process and in the next stage is the possibility of being present in it and then controlling it.

2-shapes states

by changing of weather. A space whose dimensions are weather, elevations, being enclosed or coastal. These spaces are not permanent and may be destroyed by loss and destruction of one of dimensions of space

Historical process and new horizon in contemporary geopolitics

Historical process and new horizon in contemporary geopolitics

Due to some kind of change in the climate, changes in history happen. One of the common cases of these changes happened in the south of Europe and in the north of Africa in the middle ages. The Iberian Peninsula was conquered by the Muslims and the Arabs. There are several theories about this conquest and its speed. One theory is that the climate change turned the Iberian Peninsula into a dry land without water and grass, and the Arabs were able to easily reach the north of the Iberian Peninsula. Jezizeh Iberi is ahead of them. In fact, this was a new space that was opened for the Arab people in southern Europe, and gradually the face of history changed with the establishment of the Arabs and the culture they wanted. ..(shahidipak,2000).

Historical process and new horizon in contemporary geopolitics

3- constantly unstable.

Relationship between politics and space.

Space is constantly changing, and its actors change are actors of politic . One of the issues that politics and space are connected to is the issue of the eternal and eternal myth of dividing the world. This myth existed between the great empires of Iran and Rome in the ancient period. At the beginning of the modern period, the myth of the division of the world was created by the Portuguese and Spanish empires with their domination over the seas of the world.) .shahidipak, 2018). The golden age of geopolitics was formed when all the landmasses of the earth were discovered and the powers of the world fought to seize and divide them.) Defargeres,1933).

4-place of constant danger

vast space extends from Europe to China and from Atlantic Ocean to Himalayas, there is a place of constant danger, and if a special power like Russia, China, Othman,&...flourishes in age of Tsar&....While new form of civilization is emerging, There are three permanent places and spaces in the world that are subject to the action of past history and political change and

4-1- a special power like Russia

Space: Russia is the best example of continuous performance of history in changing the new political environment and forming a new government, and it is the most active geoplactic volcano in the world. which has been activated now and the scope of its activity may have very wide quantitative and qualitative geopolitical effects in the world and cause changes in the history of the world. Russia has undergone political changes twice in the 20th and 21st centuries due to the necessity of history.. Czarist Russia partially realized the myth of dividing the world and the face of half of the world was changed by their legacy and by the hands of their successors.. Is history always a fire under the ashes in Russia? Is there still a desire to establish an empire after the collapse of the Soviet Union and the collapse of Eastern Europe?

4-2- a special power like China

China, with the longest history in the world, despite its large size and one-fifth of the world's population, is still the most stable nation and government in the world, this is the appearance of it, but China changed under the influence of history, the largest number of them after the opening of the international market to China and free relations with the world. They were addicted and then became a British colony when the opium empire fell apart in 1839 to 1860 and the collapse of the empire continued until 1949 and the communists restored the Chinese empire. In this way, China has experienced the deepest and greatest interface of history and changes. And these changes are with the capture of China by the Mongols and the collapse in the 19th century and the return in the middle of the 20th century.

4-3- a special power Othman

Since 1938, the dream of returning to the empire in the world political scene is a part of the ideological attitude of Turkey. Turkey has the historical potential and the three volcanoes of history are activated from there. Its borders are in Europe, Asia and the Middle East. The revival of the Ottoman heritage, which included Azaq, Syria, Egypt, Libya, and Algeria, was on the agenda of the tendency to revive the Ottoman Empire. The eruption of history in Turkey has the greatest potential for change due to the convergence of the interests of many big countries and Turkey's interest in being in Syria.

5 - perevent of gchanging history

Historian of civilization, Toynbee(1975) proposed transnational law to protect Atomic power(shahidipak,2019) ,As NPT, because Atomic energy is the reason for the movement of history at this point, and limiting atomic power in the hands of powers is a guarantee of preserving history and preventing them from acting. Another way to prevent nuclear power is the Raymond line initiative, Inventing a special geopolitical reform of the Rimland line is a way to prevent the action of history in the changing space. In Europe, Asia, Turkey, Iran, South Korea, Japan, Saudi Arabia, etc.

Historical process and new horizon in contemporary geopolitics

Historical process and new horizon in contemporary geopolitics

6 -Results and discussion

The interaction of geopolitics and history is an essential part of history. I have discussed the impact of history on politics angeopolitics in several articles, including the control of the geopolitical behavior of the Iranian tribes of Hazira by the caliphate. (2015).History is still the source of political changes that appear in the form of nation-state. These changes may be possible due to weather conditions, or due to the action of nature such as earthquakes and floods. They may slow down or stop.

References

- 1) Shahidipak , Mohammadreza ,(2020)An Analysis of History, Causality and Evolution in Islamic, Iranian and Polish Philosophy,International Journal of Philosophy 8 (4):104 (2020) Copy BIBTEX, 10.11648/j.ijp.20200804.14.
- 2) Shahidipak , Mohammadreza ,The theory of writing world history based on the history of the Iberian peninsula, the foreign relations of Portugal and Spain with the Safavid dynasty (13501736),Journal of New Achievements in Humanities Studies »April 2018 Number 11.
- 3) Shahidipak,Mohammadreza,Analytic history of Andalusia, 1000 university of AL-Mostafa-publisher.
- 4) Defaraj, Dictionery of geopolitic , translated by Razi,2013,contemporary culture publisher.
- 5) Shahidi Pak -Mohammad Reza, 2015-Controlling the geopolitical behavior of the Iranian peoples of the island b - establishcaliphate cities in the Middle Ages. International Conference on Engineering and Applied Sciences-Conference websitaddress: iceasconf.com- Article IOI code: XYZZ-AAFZF Direct link to the articl - <https://isnac.ir/XYZZ-AAFZF>.
- 6) Shahidipak M (2019)- Global Hypothesis of Civilization and Philosophy, Metaphysics of Sciences - August 05, 2019- Philosophy International Journal,Volume 2 Issue 3 -DOI:10.23880/phij-16000122.